

FUTURE PERSPECTIVE OF PROBIOTIC HEALTHCARE : A SEMINAR PARTICIPATION

The seminar is organised by DEPARTMENT OF BOTANY , SREE CHAITANYA COLLEGE HABRA , 24 , PGS (NORTH) , W.B , INDIA on 16.02.2016 .. It is an application of BIOTECHNOLOGICAL or MICROBIAL TECHNOLOGY to maintain ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY . KEY SPEAKER : PROF DR. JNANENDRA RATH , VISWABHARATI UNIVERSITY , SANTINIKETON , W.B , INDIA. ACKNOWLEDGE : HEAD OF THE DEPARTMENT & PRINCIPAL , SCC , HABRA , W.B.INDIA . Microbiome include Virus & Bacterial Concerns .Viral Infection is much more prominent . Probiotic therapy including Vitamins containing live spores of Lactobacillus microbes are widely used after cancer-chemotherapy .

REF :

(1) Jaydip Datta , A Photo Sensitized CHEMOTHERAPEUTIC modeled complex ,September 2019 ,DOI:[10.13140/RG.2.2.26850.25288/3](https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26850.25288/3) .

(https://www.researchgate.net/publication/335222923_A_Photo_Sensitized_CHEMOTHERAPEUTIC_modeled_complex?_sg%5B0%5D=YMIQN42A7dFYkCeungyQkzqvsJ-Cg7vE5CKIazivJD4vQNs8TE5AHYPdyIJbNinhOrz3OoG_6Utfv_5IkFLHN-VjblDjziQ1Tijx5jgk.QC1oAHjyWn75n2cbFGi_o8KZs6YzU9OCmmAVZzgBNrqN5Yg0YNUNScGz_91bsmHTlmjZg6yS7_hWDoz1aKSIHQ)

